

THE INFLUENCE OF CORROSIVE TESTING ON THE INTERFACE PROPERTIES OF POLYMER/METAL HYBRIDS: ADHESION BEHAVIOUR AND POLYMER DYNAMICS.

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ABSTRACT

Polymer/metal hybrids are of high interest for example in lightweight constructions used in the automotive industry. They combine a high functional integration with a lower weight compared to pure metal parts. The joining of these dissimilar materials without using additional material is a central challenge. Moreover, hybrids have to pass several standard test procedures including a corrosive test in order to verify their suitability in automotive applications. However, not much is known about the influence of such test on the (performance) properties of the hybrid and the polyamide component down to a molecular level.

In a first step, the metal/polymer interface is characterized with regard to the adhesion behaviour using contact angle (CA) measurements and colloidal probe atomic force microscopy (CP-AFM). With the combination of the two methods the adhesion properties on a macro- and (sub)microscopic scale can be determined in a non-destructive way. CP-AFM determines the adhesion force F_{ad} and energy E_{ad} which can be analysed and related to a work of adhesion per area W_{ad} using theoretical models of contact mechanics. The effect of a (sub)micrometre scale roughness on the adhesion is considered using the Rabinovich approach. A macroscopic adhesion is obtained from CA measurements. The surface energy of the polymer and metal component is determined using the Owens-Wendt-Rabel-Kaelble (OWRK) method and values are further be related to the corresponding W_{ad} per area.

In a second step, broadband dielectric spectroscopy measurements in a wide frequency (10^{-2} to 10^7 Hz) and temperature range (-120 to 180 °C) are performed in order to characterize the polymer propertie before and after corrosion testing. The dielectric spectra can be decomposed into local and segmental relaxation modes. In addition a Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars relaxation can be observed which intensity and position changes after corrosion testing.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastics are widely used in the field of engineering thermoplastics due to their excellent mechanical properties and easy processability. They find a broad variety of applications, e.g. in metal/polymer hybrids (PMH) for the automotive industry where the use of plastics increases with the demand to reduce weight and increase fuel efficiency

The adhesion between the metal and polymeric materials plays a major role in many industrial fields for example in lightweight constructions used in the automotive, aircraft and aerospace industry. A fundamental understanding about the adhesion mechanisms at the metal/polymer interface on different length scales is essential. Various tests to measure adhesion properties in a direct way exist including peel-test, lap shear test, torque test, scratch test and pull-off test.[1,2] However, most of these methods are not only destructive but also not suited to reveal adhesion information on a micro- or even nanoscopic level. In the present work a non-destructive multiscale approach is used to

investigate the adhesion behaviour between metals and polymers using atomic force microscopy (AFM) and contact angle (CA) measurements.

Polymer/metal hybrids parts have to pass several standard test procedures including a corrosive test in order to verify their suitability in automotive applications. However, not much is known about the influence of such test on (1) the adhesion properties between the metal and polymer and (2) the performance properties of the polymer component. Adhesion studies are performed between a dual phase steel (DPS) and polyamide 6 (PA6) before and after corrosion treatment using AFM and CA measurements. For a more detailed study of the polymer properties down to a molecular level dielectric relaxation spectroscopy (DRS) is applied before and after the corrosion test. DRS is a powerful tool to evaluate the different molecular mobilities and conductivity phenomena in the polymer samples in a non-destructive way.

The paper starts with a theoretical part discussing briefly (1) the analysis of force curves obtained from AFM measurements and the influence of surface roughness on measured adhesion forces and (2) the theoretical background of dielectric relaxation spectroscopy. The result section presents first adhesion properties from CA measurements and AFM force measurements before and after corrosion treatment. Subsequently, the dielectric properties are discussed.

2 THEORY

2.1 ATOMIC FORCE MICROSCOPY – FORCE MEASUREMENTS

AFM has become an important method to measure adhesion forces on a (sub)micrometer scale in a direct way. Using the colloidal probe (CP) technique introduced in 1991 by Ducker et al. [3] it is possible to detect adhesion forces between a probe and a substrate on a micro- and nanoscopic length scale. The technique is well-established for studying the surface interactions and mechanical properties between all kinds of colloidal particles and surfaces including not only the field of material science but also biological and pharmaceutical systems. A review about the technique and its application in adhesion measurements can be found in literature.[4] The basic concept of CP-AFM is the measurement of forces between a particle (microsphere) attached to the end of a cantilever and a sample surface. A typical force-distance curve for a metal substrate and a PA6 microsphere is shown in Figure 1. The single steps are basically (1) the microsphere approach to the sample surface, (2) the jump-to-contact point, where the sphere is attracted towards the surface followed by (3) sample indentation or compliance without deformation and cantilever deflection and (4) the retraction of the sphere which might be hindered by adhesive forces. The adhesion force F_{ad} between the colloidal probe and the sample is given by Hooke's law:

$$F_{ad} = -k_c \delta_{jump-off} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where k_c is the spring constant and $\delta_{jump-off}$ the jump-off-contact cantilever deflection.

Figure 1: Typical experimental force-distance curve between a PA6 microsphere and a metal surface.

The adhesion forces F_{ad} can be related to a work of adhesion W_{ad} using contact mechanics models. Two contact models are often used: the Johnson- Kendall-Robert (JKR) model derived by Johnson et al.[5] in 1971 and the Derjaguin-Müller-Toporov (DMT) model derived by Derjaguin et al.[6] in 1975. Both are based on the Hertz theory.[7] For both models the correlation between F_{ad} and W_{ad} is described through a simple analytical equation as follows:

$$F_{ad} = c\pi RW_{ad} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where R is the radius of the microsphere attached to the cantilever and c is a constant with $c= 2$ in the DMT and $c= 1.5$ in the JKR model.

The JKR and DMT models assume a spherical particle in contact with a smooth surface, i.e. two ideal geometries. However, most materials have rough surfaces altering the true contact area between the colloidal probe and substrate from that predicted. Roughness must be taken into account when interpreting experimentally measured AFM adhesion forces. Various studies can be found in literature dealing with the influence of surface roughness on measured adhesion forces by AFM. [8,9,10,11] A model to estimate adhesion forces for nanoscale rough surfaces has been described by Rumpf.[12] Based on the Rumpf model a modified and extended model has been proposed by Rabinovich et al.[13,14] The aim is to model the surface roughness in a way that describes the surface geometry of the substrate more precise. It considers roughness on two different scales. If only one roughness scale is detectable or relevant as in the present work, the Rabinovich model reads:

$$F_{ad} = \frac{c\pi W_{ad} R r_2}{r_2 + R} + \frac{AR}{6H_0^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{1.82(rms)}{H_0}\right)^2} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where A is the Hamaker constant, H_0 the distance of closest approach between the contacting surfaces (~ 0.3 nm), rms the root mean square roughness and λ the peak-to-peak distance. The radius of asperity, r_2 , can be replaced by:[14]

$$r_2 = \frac{\lambda^2}{58rms} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

2.2 DIELECTRIC RELAXATION SPECTROSCOPY

Dielectric spectroscopy is sensitive to molecular fluctuations of dipoles within the system which are related to the molecular mobility of groups, segments, or whole polymer chains. For details see Ref. [15]. Another contribution to the dielectric response is the polarization due to charge migration or separation. Free charge carriers (electrons, ions) move across the sample under the influence of an outer electric field and cause conductivity. In addition, moving charge carriers can accumulate at internal interfaces (phase boundaries) or electrodes causing an additional polarization known as Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars (MWS) polarization[16] or electrode polarization, respectively. In the case of semi-crystalline polymers, such as PA6, differences in conductivity of the amorphous and crystalline phase give rise to a MWS polarization. The contribution to the dielectric response can be much larger than the response due to molecular fluctuations. The conductivity of the amorphous domains increases with increasing temperature while the crystalline phase is not electrically conducting. Free charges are hindered in their motion and trapped at the boundaries between crystalline and amorphous phase. The relaxation time of the MWS polarization is inversely proportional to the conductivity of the material. With increasing conductivity the relaxation time decreases which means the process is shifted to higher frequencies. The MWS polarization can overlap with other relaxation processes. The total dielectric response is the sum of the contributions mentioned above. They can be distinguished by showing specific characteristics in the frequency and temperature dependence of the real and imaginary part of the dielectric function.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

3.1. METHODS

AFM force measurements: Force-distance curves were collected via an atomic force microscope (MFP3D, Asylum Research, CA, USA). Measurements were conducted in a dry nitrogen atmosphere at a constant temperature of 30 °C using a Poly Heater™ cell (Asylum Research, CA, USA) that can be fully sealed with a membrane. The humidity was kept under RH 5 % throughout the whole measurement by flushing dry nitrogen through the cell. Statistical data evaluation is needed for a proper interpretation of the adhesion forces. Force maps including 100 single force-distance curves obtained over an area of 90×90 μm were recorded. At least 5 different locations of the sample were mapped. The adhesion force is obtained from the minimum of the data of the retraction curve. An adhesion histogram was generated from the results and mean and standard deviation were calculated by fitting a Gaussian distribution to the histogram.

Contact angle measurements: The adhesion on a macroscopic scale was calculated from contact angle (CA) measurements using the Owens-Wendt-Rabel-Kaelble (OWRK) method.[17,18] Compared to AFM, CA measurements determine the work of adhesion between two solid components in an indirect way. However, information such as the division of the surface energy into dispersive and polar components can be obtained. CA measurements were performed using the sessile drop method using a Goniometer OCA20 (Dataphysics, Germany).

Dielectric measurements: The PA6 plates were placed between two gold-coated electrodes (15mm in diameter) in parallel geometry. The complex dielectric function is derived by measuring the complex impedance $Z^*(\omega)$. Measurements were carried out in a frequency range from 10^{-1} to 10^7 Hz at temperatures between -120 and 180 °C with a high-resolution ALPHA analyzer (Novocontrol, Hundsangen, Germany). The temperature is controlled by a Quatro Novocontrol cryosystem with a temperature stability of 0.1 K.

3.2 SAMPLES

PA6 samples for dielectric studies: A commercially available polyamide 6 (PA6) was used. Plates of 20×20 mm with a thickness of 1-2 mm were prepared by injection moulding. The PA6 plates were cleaned in pure ethanol in the ultrasonic bath for 5min and subsequently dried under a nitrogen stream. For dielectric studies gold electrodes with a diameter of 15 mm were evaporated from both sides. Prior to measurements samples were dried under vacuum at 60 °C for 4 h.

PA6 samples for adhesion studies: For AFM measurements polymeric microspheres made of PA6 (Phosphorex Inc., USA) with a diameter of around 20 +/- 7 μm are used. The microspheres are glued with epoxy to a tipless cantilever with a given spring constant of 5 to 17 N/m (NSC35 MikroMasch). Microspheres were characterized by optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) in order to obtain information about size and surface roughness.

Metal substrate: A dual phase steel (DPS) commonly used in industrial applications is used. Technical surfaces exhibit a quite rough surface (micrometer range) not suitable for AFM investigations. Therefore the DPS samples was mechanically polished in order to obtain a rather smooth surface with a nm scaled roughness. A careful analysis of the surface roughness is necessary in order to evaluate the measured adhesion forces.

Figure 2: *Left:* AFM image of polished DPS sample. *Right:* SEM image of a PA6 microsphere (recorded at ZELMI, TU Berlin).

3.3 CORROSION TREATMENT

The PA6 samples (microspheres and plates) were tested following a standard corrosion test procedure. The procedure and test parameters are sketched in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Procedure and parameters for corrosion test.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 ADHESION BEHAVIOUR

Macroscopic adhesion: Table 1 lists the surface energy γ_s of the polymer and metal sample (PA6 and DPS) determined using the OWRK method. The results agree well with surface energies found in literature for the respective material. Note that metals have in general a high surface energy whereas polymers are low surface energy materials. However, a native oxide layer and organic contamination on the metal surface reduce the surface energy of the metal. Thus the total surface energy of the metal and polymer sample is of the same magnitude. Using the surface energies a macroscopic work of adhesion $W_{ad,CA}$ can be calculated. Between PA6 and DPS that results in 82.6 mN/m (see Table 1).

Sample	Total surface energy per area γ_s [mN/m]	Dispersive part γ_s^d [mN/m]	Polar Part γ_s^p [mN/m]	Work of adhesion per area $W_{ad,CA}$ [mN/m]
PA6	42.5 +/- 3.1	37.0 +/- 0.7	5.5 +/- 2.4	82.6 +/- 6.7
DPS	40.9 +/- 3.3	31.2 +/- 1.2	9.5 +/- 2.1	

Table 1: Total surface energy per area with dispersive and polar part for PA6 and DPS and calculated work of adhesion per area between the two components.

Microscopic adhesion: Figure 4 shows the adhesion force between PA6 and DPS obtained from

CP-AFM. Force data are plotted in a histogram and fitted with a Gaussian line. The corresponding mean adhesion force F_{ad} and the standard deviation are given in the graph. The reference sample shows a mean adhesion force of about 700 nN. After corrosion testing of the polymer component (see Figure 3) two peaks in the force histogram are visible with a low and high mean adhesion force of 182 and 1457 nN, respectively. The origin of the adhesion force distribution after corrosion testing is not clear yet and further experiments are running. In the following only the adhesion behaviour of the reference system is discussed.

Figure 4: Adhesion force F_{ad} histogram obtained from AFM force mapping for DPS/PA6 (a) before corrosion testing and (b) after corrosion testing of PA6. The solid lines are Gaussian fits to the data.

Raw data from AFM force measurements have to be evaluated with care. In order to have more conclusive results a detailed analysis considering roughness effects of sphere and substrate is necessary. Moreover adhesion forces should be related to a work of adhesion per area W_{ad} in order to compare macro- and microscopic adhesion results. W_{ad} was calculated in the framework of the Rabinovich model using Equation 3. Values for Hamaker constants are taken from literature. The Hamaker between DPS/PA6, A_{12} , is $1.09 \cdot 10^{-19}$ J. The microscopic work of adhesion $W_{ad,AFM}$ results in 73.5 mN/m which is slightly smaller compared the work of adhesion obtained from CA measurements but in the same order of magnitude. That means there is a good correlation between macro- and microscopic adhesion and no length-scale dependent adhesion behavior can be found.

4.1 POLYMER DYNAMICS BEFORE AND AFTER CORROSION TESTING

The isochronal graph at 1 kHz, Figure 5a, shows the temperature dependence of the imaginary part of the permittivity ϵ'' for PA6_{Ref} (reference sample) and PA6_C (after corrosion testing).

Figure 5: (a) Temperature dependence of ϵ'' for PA6_{Ref} (black squares) and the PA6_C (blue triangles) at a frequency of 1 kHz. The different relaxation processes are indicated. (b) Temperature dependence of M'' for PA6_{Ref} (black squares) and the PA6_C (blue triangles) at a frequency of 1 kHz.

The main relaxation processes identified are: (1) the γ -relaxation appearing at temperatures between -120 and -20 °C. It is mainly associated with the local motion of the chain segments ($-\text{CH}_2-$

sequences) involving dipolar amide groups. (2) The β -relaxation centered between -65 and 20 °C. It is more related to the local motion of the polar chain segments (-NH-CO-) involving water molecules hydrogen bonded to the free NH groups. (3) The segmental α -relaxation occurring between 40 and 125 °C. It is related to the glass-rubber transition of PA6 and can be decomposed into a wet and dry α -relaxation, i.e. a plasticized and non-plasticized mode. (4) The MWS relaxation process visible in the high temperature regime between 55 and 180 °C arising from charge carriers accumulated at the interphase between amorphous and crystalline regions. The four processes are typically for polyamide samples and could be observed for both samples, before and after corrosion testing. However differences between the two samples in are noted, especially in the higher temperature regime, where the MWS is located. However, the peak is superimposed by electrode polarization effects and can therefore not be clearly extracted in the permittivity spectra. Using the complex electric modulus formalism, electrode polarization effects can be suppressed and the MWS relaxation is visible as a peak in the imaginary part of the complex dielectric modulus as shown in Figure 5b.

After the corrosion test (a) a clear change in the higher temperature regime of the dielectric spectra is observed with a shift of the MWS relaxation to lower temperatures and (b) the β -relaxation of PA6_C is shifted to higher temperatures. In the following the isochronal data are analyzed using dielectric model functions.

Figure 6: Relaxation map for PA6_{Ref} (black squares) and the PA6_C (blue triangles). The solid lines are fits to the data (Arrhenius and VFT). The fit parameters are reported in Table 2 and Table 3.

From the fitting of the isothermal data to a Cole-Cole function [19] the relaxation rate f_p is obtained. It is plotted versus reciprocal temperature in Figure 6 for PA6_{Ref} (reference sample) and PA6_C (after corrosion testing). For the γ - and β - relaxation the temperature dependence of $\log f_p$ follows the Arrhenius equation indicating a thermal activated behavior and non-cooperative motions. For the MWS process the temperature dependence of $\log f_p$ is curved when plotted versus $1000/T$. It can be described by the Vogel-Fulcher-Tammann (VFT) equation [20] indication cooperative motions.

Sample	γ - relaxation		β - relaxation	
	E_A [kJ/mol]	$\log(f_\infty$ [Hz])	E_A [kJ/mol]	$\log(f_\infty$ [Hz])
PA6 Reference	35.4	13.1	49.6	13.2
PA6 after corrosion testing	39.2	14.1	75.7	17.7

Table 2: Parameters obtained from Arrhenius fit for PA6 samples.

The activation energy E_A of the γ - relaxation is not influenced by the corrosion test. Values are 35.4 and 39.2 kJ/mol for PA6_{Ref} and PA6_C, respectively. That is comparable to literature values for neat PA6 samples. Compared to the γ - relaxation, the Arrhenius plots of the β - relaxation show differences

in the slope of the linear dependence for PA6_{Ref} and PA6_C (see Figure 6). The corresponding activation energies are 49.6 and 75.7 kJ/mol for PA6_{Ref} and PA6_C, respectively. The β -relaxation is related to the local motion of the polar chain segments involving water molecules hydrogen bonded to the free NH groups. The increase in E_A after the corrosion test might be explained by remaining salt ions and/or complexes that interact with the polar groups and interchain hydrogen bonds. The fluctuations are hindered and the energy barrier increases.

Sample	MWS relaxation			
	$\log(f_\omega [\text{Hz}])$	$A_0 [\text{K}]$	$T_0^{\text{id}} [\text{K}]$	$D = A_0 / T_0^{\text{id}}$
PA6 Reference	8.5	394.0	238.3	1.7
PA6 after corrosion testing	8.2	239.3	266.3	0.9

Table 3. Parameters obtained from VFT fit for PA6 samples.

The temperature dependence of the relaxation rate of the MWS process is described by a VFT fit. The fitting resulted in differences regarding the T_0^{id} which is called ideal glass transition or Vogel temperature. It is found to be 30-70 K below the thermal glass transition temperature.[21] After the corrosion test, the PA6 sample shows a higher T_0^{id} meaning that the glass transition temperature T_g is slightly increased for PA6_C compared to the reference sample.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The metal/polymer interface is characterized with regard to the adhesion behaviour using contact angle (CA) measurements and colloidal probe atomic force microscopy (CP-AFM). The adhesion properties on a macro- and (sub)microscopic scale for a PA6/DPS hybrid were determined in a non-destructive way. The work of adhesion per are W_{ad} was found to be in the same order of magnitude for the two length scales with a macroscopic W_{ad} of 82.6 mN/m and a microscopic W_{ad} of 73.5 mN/m. In the latter case the effect of a (sub)micrometre scale roughness on the adhesion properties was considered using the Rabinovich approach. The influence of a corrosion treatment on the adhesion behaviour is investigated. However, no clear results are obtained yet.

Complementary, broadband dielectric spectroscopy measurements were carried out before and after corrosion testing in order to study the polymer properties down to a molecular level. It was found that the local β -relaxation and the interfacial MWS polarization were sensitive to the corrosion test procedure. Two main changes in the dielectric spectra of PA6 are observed after corrosion testing: (1) A higher activation energy for the β -relaxation process which is shifted to higher temperatures and (2) An increased intensity of the MWS relaxation which is shifted to lower temperatures. The changes in the dielectric spectra are caused by remaining salt ions in the sample. The mobile charge carriers enhance the conductivity of the sample and shift the MWS relaxation to higher frequencies. Moreover, the salt ions or complexes interact with the polar amide groups and/or the intrachain hydrogen bonds between them and hinder the rotational motion of the process.

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